

Procedural Due Process in Tax Law and the Human Rights *Doctrine* in Europe (the *Italgomme Case*)

by Marco Greggi*

1. INTRODUCTION

The European Convention on Human Rights, signed in 1950 and now ratified by 47 European countries¹, remains the most effective legal instrument for providing basic protection to individuals whose rights are under threat on the continent.

Although it is not the only charter to safeguard the basic liberties of each individual², and irrespective of its regional importance, the success of the Conventions derives from both the fact that an independent and supranational Court has been established to adjudicate possible violations of it (the European Court on Human Rights) and from the commitment by the Council of Europe to enforce the Court's judgments³.

When the Convention was signed, taxation was neither on the agenda of the parties nor probably in their minds. The 1950s were years in which Europe had other priorities, including the necessity to bridge a widening gap between East and West, and to foster human dignity in a way that would prevent disasters like World War II. Individual liberties, due process of law, protection of family life, religious beliefs and, eventually, property were among the rights mentioned in the Convention and in the annexed protocols.

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¹ Carla M. Buckley et al., *The European Convention on Human Rights: Principles and Law* (Council of Europe, 2022).

² Myres S McDougal et al., *Human Rights and World Public Order: The Basic Policies of an International Law of Human Dignity*, 2^a ed. (Oxford University Press, 2019), <https://doi.org/10.1093/law/9780190882631.001.0001>.

³ Articles 1 and 46 of the ECHR

The lack of any explicit mention of taxation did not stop the Court from broadening the scope of the Convention to include fiscal matters, however⁴.

In the last two decades, an increasing number of tax cases have been decided by the Court of Strasbourg, which has made the most of the purposive interpretation of the Convention. For instance, the protection of property⁵ (taken in conjunction with the right to non-discrimination) has been used to judge as contrary to human rights a decision to tax individuals or companies disproportionately.

More recently, the Court has further extended the Convention's influence on procedural elements of taxation⁶.

The Court ruled that human rights influence not only the amount of taxes imposed but also the manner in which they are applied. More specifically, audit procedures, inspections, and controls on taxpayers suspected of evading taxes or whose compliance is under review must be conducted in accordance with certain fundamental rights: this is particularly true when during these procedures administrative sanctions are charged on the taxpayer who has violated the law⁷.

The latest case in this respect (so far), the *Italgomme*⁸, represents a landmark decision in this area. Far from being just a standalone precedent, the decision made by the Court is part of a long-standing trend⁹ focused on emphasising the protection of human rights in procedural aspects related to taxation. In the Court's view, human rights are relevant not only to the substantive aspects of taxation but also to procedural issues: that is, how the tax authorities conduct inspections, the impact on personal privacy, the duration of audits, and their potentially disruptive effects on the daily lives of taxpayers.

This research aims to investigate the impact that the *Italgomme* doctrine might have, and to achieve this goal, it is divided into three major parts.

In the first one, the procedural due process principle will be examined regarding its relevance in European law and its actual impact on the domestic tax system.

⁴ P. Van der Broek, «Taxation and the European Convention on Human Rights», *European taxation* 25, fasc. 12 (1985): 344–48; P. Baker, «Taxation and the European Convention on Human Rights in the domestic law of the Council of Europe countries : introduction», *European taxation* 41, fasc. 12 (2001): 459–61.

⁵ Article 1, first Protocol to the European convention on Human rights. See also Marco Gregg, «Human Rights as Supranational Limits to Tax Law. A European Contribute to the Mediterranean Area.», 2010, 1:305–38.

⁶ P. J. Panuthos, «Procedural issues of human rights and taxation : access to justice», *Bulletin for international taxation* 71, fasc. 7 (2017): 390–95.

⁷ Marco Gregg, «The protection of Human Rights and the Right to a Fair Tax Trial in the Light of the Jussila case», *Intertax* 35, fasc. 11 (2007): 610–15.

⁸ *Italgomme Pneumatici S.R.L. and others v. Italy* (no. 36617/18), 6 February 2025.

⁹ S. N. Frommel, «The European Court of Human Rights and taxpayers : the right to a fair trial», *Tax notes international* 8, fasc. 26 (194d.C.): 1723–28.

In the second part, the *Italgomme* case will be examined. In this regard, particular emphasis will be placed on the connection between procedural aspects and the rule of law principle, as highlighted by the Court of Human Rights.

In the third part, the taxpayers' fundamental right will be reconceptualised within the framework of the decision and the case law of the ECHR on the matter.

In conclusion, we will emphasise the necessity for an intervention by the European Union on the matter, as asymmetric protection of procedural rights could ultimately cause distortion in the common market, and that negative integration through court decisions, despite being positive, remains inadequate in establishing a level playing field. We will observe that, although *Italgomme* has been a decision of paramount importance for European taxpayers, nonetheless it can be considered just a step forward in a still long journey

2. THE PROCEDURAL ASPECTS OF DUE PROCESS IN TAX LAW

The due process clause is a fundamental pillar of the rule of law¹⁰. No state can claim to be governed by the rule of law if the Courts' adjudication authority does not align with the due process clause.

While the consistency with such a clause is essential, its actual scope has never been clearly defined. Although extensively debated, there are still different interpretations regarding its true reach. For some, it simply requires predictability of decisions¹¹; for others, it emphasises the need to consider justice, fairness, and other substantive values. Some others connect it with specific political values¹².

Regardless of differing views on the issue, the prevailing stance is that the "Due process" clause is essentially a subset of the conditions that must be satisfied by an adjudicative procedure. This procedure is conducted and guided by an impartial public officer, such as a judge, who remains neutral towards the parties, unbiased, and bound only by the law¹³. Within these procedures, parties have the right to be heard, to present their case and arguments, to offer evidence, and to request additional evidence to support their claims, which the judge gathers.

¹⁰ Article 6 ECHR. P. Van Dijk e G. J. H. Van Hoof, *Theory and practice of the European Convention on Human Rights* (Kluwer, 1984).

¹¹ Joseph Raz, *The Authority of Law: Essays on Law and Morality*, 2nd edition (Oxford university press, 2009). In particular pp. 210 and *sub*.

¹² Zhang Wenxian, «Adhering to the Establishment of the System of Socialist Rule of Law with Chinese Characteristics», *China Legal Science* 29, fasc. 10 (2022): 41–60. See also Jinping Xi, «Adhere to the Road of Socialist Rule of Law with Chinese Characteristics and Better Promote the Construction of the System of Socialist Rule of Law with Chinese Characteristics», *Qiushi Journal*, fasc. 4 (2022): 6–9.

¹³ Frommel, «The European Court of Human Rights and taxpayers : the right to a fair trial».

The judge, on their part, has the authority to collect evidence (sometimes by searching for it), to command the parties and potential witnesses to appear, and to exercise additional powers as stipulated by law. In some legal systems, due process also encompasses the ability to appeal a sentence or to lodge an appeal to the Supreme Court for a breach of the law, although the literature remains unclear on this issue.

While a common understanding of due process exists between states, the same is not true for procedural due process, whose existence is sometimes contested, as it lacks specific references in law like the due process clause¹⁴.

“Procedural due process” (or “Due procedure”) involves expanding the scope of individual rights within the (administrative) procedure, as regulated across different areas of law. If this principle is adopted, the individual (in our case, the taxpayer) would have the right to be heard, to present evidence, and to cross-examine evidence from the office well before the process begins, with such rights only being restricted where extraordinary and overriding needs exist — for example, in cases of criminal investigations where secrecy in the early phases is essential to uncover the truth and secure evidence.

From a theoretical perspective, theorists such as Hans Kelsen¹⁵ pointed out that the process is a specific kind of procedure, with the only difference being that during the process, the person in charge (the judge) is independent and acts as a third party in decision-making. In most procedures, however, the person in charge is part of the public administration and, as such, is subject to the law as well as other regulations issued by the government or, more broadly, the executive power. Furthermore, the person in charge during the procedure is almost never independent, as they are routinely subject to the directives of someone else, making them unable to decide solely according to the law like the judge.

Procedures mostly occur in the exercise of executive powers, while processes depend on the judiciary (or judiciary functions that on some occasions can be exercised outside the judiciary). This is a distinction that has been debated for centuries, perhaps in the context of continental administrative law.

With the dogmatic idea of “procedure” came the necessity to regulate it and find the conditions under which a procedure could be considered as consistent with the law: both continental law and common law admit the possibility of judicial review of most procedures¹⁶, thus implicitly recognising the primacy of the rule of law, with the only exception being political decisions.

¹⁴ Thomas Henry Bingham of Cornhill, *The Rule of Law* (Penguin Books, 2011).

¹⁵ Hans Kelsen, *Pure Theory of Law* (The Lawbook Exchange, 2020), <https://doi.org/10.1525/9780520312296>.

¹⁶ Jonathan Auburn, *Judicial Review: Principles and Procedure*, (Oxford University Press, Incorporated, 2013).

Although every human activity can be considered a procedure, not all are legally relevant. Most legal systems recognise relevance only in those outcomes that could affect the personal sphere of individuals or entities (natural or legal persons).

Every part of the law includes procedures that must be followed to achieve legal effects. For example, when a company raises capital by issuing new shares, a vote is typically required from the shareholders' assembly. To ensure proper notification, shareholders need a specific invitation or a call from the CEO or equivalent managers, administered in accordance with the rules applicable in the company's respective state. Some of these steps are procedures nested within others (referred to as sub-procedures). For instance, the voting process is governed by provisions that may allow anonymity, the timely exercise of rights, and other considerations. Violations of these procedures—such as raising capital without shareholder consensus or miscalculating votes—may ultimately lead to the invalidity of such actions or other legal consequences, as regulated by law.

Although procedures are important in all areas of law, they play a particularly crucial role in managing the public interest. This is why, in most legal systems, procedures are studied within administrative law or other areas where they serve to protect individuals from the arbitrary exercise of power by the authority (such as in Criminal law).

The procedure, *per se*, is meant as a way to protect the individual from the discretionary exercise of powers. No procedure is perhaps conceivable without the separation of powers and the rule of law. Some authors argue that, through the procedure, form prevails over substance¹⁷.

Taxation is no exception to this, even though most legal systems regard tax rules as a subset of administrative law. Imposing a tax negatively affects an individual's wealth, as it prejudices their possessions. Of course, such prejudice is justified under the law when pursuing other rights and legitimate interests deemed more important, such as the common good, the need for greater social solidarity, and so on. This primacy is often recognised in the constitution of the state.

Taxation is a necessary evil, or the price of civilisation¹⁸, as it has been said: it has an adverse effect on the individual. Consequently, it makes perfect sense that the application of taxes and the audit and control powers of the Tax administration are in accordance with the law and take place through proper procedures. Some authors argue that these procedures should also adhere to the law. They must be 'due'.

However, while there is a reasonable understanding of the meaning of 'due process', the scope and nature of 'due procedure' remain uncertain and somewhat obscure: in fact, the

¹⁷ Natalino Irti, *Il salvagente della forma*, 2. ed, Libri del tempo Laterza 402 (GLF Ed. Laterza, 2007).

¹⁸ Dissenting opinion by Justice Oliver Wendell Holmes, Jr. in U.S. Supreme Court Case, *Compania General de Tabacos de Filipinas v. Collector of Internal*, 275 U.S. 87, Argued and Submitted Oct. 18, 1927; Decided Nov. 21, 1927.

connection between ‘due’ and ‘procedure’ has mostly been explored by academics rather than in the courts. In the field of taxation, several authors have argued for the existence of fundamental rights or due procedure conditions, but without precise legal references¹⁹.

Irrespective of the lack of a clear and robust reference to the law, ‘due procedure’ under law entails the necessity of the taxpayer of being heard, the necessity to motivate any decision taken by the office, the possibility by the taxpayer to have access to the documents used by the tax office to justify the audit and the reason why a reassessment decision has been issued, *inter alia*.

Recently, the literature has focused on the need to provide taxpayers with an adversarial procedure during audits and tax inspections, not just afterwards. In this regard, the Court of Justice of the European Union has ruled²⁰ that such a procedure should be granted, allowing for judicial review of administrative decisions upon the taxpayer’s request during audits and inspections. Furthermore, the Court noted that this approach would also uphold the principle of good governance²¹, linking effective (tax) governance with taxpayers’ rights.

Consistent with this approach, authors argued that an intrinsic duty of fairness, transparency, and accountability exists and should be enforced by all tax administrations in the European Union²². Such a duty of diligence includes the necessity to involve the individual (whenever possible and to the greatest extent possible) in the decision-making process concerning their position.

In taxation law, the principle of good tax administration²³ requires tax authorities to hear the taxpayer, record their position, and justify why they consider the case to be one of tax evasion. Additionally, it would necessitate that tax inspections be reasonable and respect the taxpayer's fundamental rights under scrutiny.

Reasonable as it sounds, such an argument still lacked formal acknowledgement in case law beyond the specific situation in which it was mentioned and a solid reference to generally applicable provisions. This latest step was taken by the European Court of Human Rights in *Italgomme*, where the necessity of ‘due process’ was linked to human rights.

¹⁹ Marco Greggi e Iacopo Buriani, «La CEDU e il principio del giusto procedimento» in I principi europei del diritto tributario, a cura di A. Di Pietro e T. Tassani, vol. 7, Diritto tributario europeo (Padova, 2014), 117.

²⁰ CJEU, 6 October 2020, Joined Cases C-245-19 and C-246/19, *Luxembourg v B and Others*, ECLI:EU:C:2020:795 (“Ruling”); see also CJEU, 22 Oct. 2013, Case C-276/12, *Jiří Sabou v. Finanční ředitelství pro hlavní město Prahu*, ECLI:EU:C:2013:678; CJEU, 16 May 2017, Case C-682/15, *Berlioz Investment Fund SA v. Directeur de l’administration des Contributions directes*, ECLI:EU:C:2017:373.

²¹ Irma Johanna Mosquera Valderrama, «The EU Standard of Good Governance in Tax Matters for Third (Non-EU) Countries», *Intertax* 47, fasc. Issue 5 (2019): 454–67, <https://doi.org/10.54648/TAXI2019046>.

²² Art. 41, Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (2000/C 364/01).

²³ See note 21 *supra*.

3. PROCEDURAL RIGHTS AND THE HUMAN RIGHTS CONVENTION IN *ITALGOMME*

The European Convention on Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms contains no specific rules affecting tax law²⁴, nor does it specify how taxes should be charged or the powers delegated to the tax authorities in auditing taxpayers. However, the lack of statutory law in this area has been addressed by the European Court of Human Rights, which interprets the Convention purposively: in this regard, the decades-long case law has already been thoroughly examined in the literature²⁵.

Recently, the Court has begun addressing the procedural aspects of tax law, making the most of the provisions in the Convention that might be potentially applicable in this case. These include, among others, articles 8 and 6: namely, respect for personal life and the right to a fair trial, although the possible application of the second provision to tax law has been questioned in the past.

The circumstances of the case *Italgomme* proved to be an ideal scenario for testing this theoretical approach, aiming to determine the extent to which the Court aimed to uphold the protection of human rights, ultimately rethinking the ‘due procedure’ clause.

The case involved a series of tax inspections initiated in Italy targeting several businesses that allegedly failed to pay the due amounts of income and VAT taxes.

The inspections of the case took place on the premises of the businesses and were conducted in accordance with the legislation relevant to the case, which, however, does not provide clear guidance to the authority carrying out the control. As a consequence, the tax office enjoys a remarkable leeway in operating on-site controls, including access to taxpayers’ premises in search of documents or evidence of tax evasion. Such flexibility is allied by the condition under which these searches may take place, as in most of the cases the warrant can be issued by the (local) director of the tax office without any judicial supervision or approval. Only in cases where the searches and inspection take place in the private home of the taxpayer, such an approval is needed, but the State Attorney (i.e. the Public Prosecutor) is the authority supposed to issue it²⁶.

The cases were challenged before the ECHR on several grounds. These would include, in particular: the fact that the inspection (and access to the premises) can be initiated outside the control of any judicial authority; that no actual judicial review is possible during the audit, should the authority violate any fundamental right of the taxpayer during the on-site inspection; that although a permission to initiate the procedure is needed from the superior administrative authority, the lack thereof does not affect the validity of the audit

²⁴ The only textual reference to taxation is contained in article 1 of the First additional protocol.

²⁵ P. Baker, «Some recent decisions of the European Court of Human Rights on tax matters (and related decisions of the European Court of Justice)», *European taxation* 56, fasc. 8 (2016): 342–51.

²⁶ Art. 52, Presidential decree n. 633 issued on 22 October 1972 (introducing VAT in Italy).

and the evidence collected; that such permission may be granted discretionally by the supervising administrative authority; and that even in cases where the inspection addresses the domicile of the taxpayer (and the authorisation of the state attorney is needed), the irregularity of the latter does not impact on the validity of the audit.

Eventually, although tax inspections in the Italian system are not coercive (thus the taxpayer may always refuse to collaborate or to allow entry to the tax police conducting the investigation), such denial has serious consequences: firstly, a fine is imposed²⁷, and secondly, the taxpayer might be exposed to more aggressive forms of presumptive audit²⁸ (that is, the tax office is allowed to argue the case against the taxpayer based on presumptions of tax evasion).

Additionally, the taxpayer is required to voluntarily disclose to the tax office any document relevant to the audit: failure to do so would prevent them from submitting the documents at a later stage of the proceedings, including during the process²⁹.

In general terms, three critical issues arise from this; and in particular, whether: (1) it is possible to initiate a tax audit without informing the taxpayer of the reason for such necessity; (2) it is permissible for an audit procedure to proceed without clear guidance from the law; and consequently, (3) a tax audit without effective judicial review is admissible. Other points were also raised in *Italgomme*, but these three issues take precedence in the Court's decision-making process. Despite their differences, they ultimately lead to the same question.

Italgomme addresses the delicate balance between the power of the (tax) authority and the primacy of law, hence the 'due process' legislation. The key issue is whether tax *exceptionalism* justifies a looser constraint on the tax administration's authority or not.

The Court proved that this was not the case³⁰, and that procedural rights must be respected, implicitly concluding that tax exceptionalism does not extend to the inspection procedure, and that human rights must prevail. More generally, it affirms that effective judicial review must be granted.

4. HUMAN RIGHTS IN ACTION: DEFINING THE LIMITS OF PRIVATE LIFE IN TAX INSPECTIONS

Although three articles of the ECHR have been used to reach the conclusions in the case, Article 8 (Respect for private life) is actually the key element in the Court's decision-making process.

²⁷ Article 9, Legislative Decree n. 471 of 18 December 1997; Article 55 § 2 (1) of Presidential decree n. 633/72 and Article 39 § 2 (c) of Presidential decree n. 600, 16 October 1973.

²⁸ This consequence is analysed at § 78 of *Italgomme*.

²⁹ Article 52, § 5 Presidential decree 633/72 cited above.

³⁰ See §§ 82 – 85 of *Italgomme*.

The provision safeguards each individual's personal sphere from intrusive activity by the authority, including implicitly the tax authority. Such intrusions, to align with this principle, must be regulated by law and carried out in accordance with it, potentially under the oversight of the judiciary: the sole entity empowered to balance the individual's rights with the prerogatives of the state³¹.

It is not the first time that the power of inspection by the tax administration is tested in this respect³²: essentially every inspection and every access to the private life sphere of an individual (or of a company) conflicts with these individual rights.

Legislators and constitutions strike a balance between the opposite necessities in play: on one side respect for personal liberty and on the other the necessity to secure the interests of the state. In the case of taxation, such interest is defined in the necessity to curb tax evasion.

The balance is primarily determined by the method chosen to decide whose interest should prevail, and it involves the role of the judiciary.

Judicial control, hence, the possibility for a magistrate to oversee the activity of the tax administration, is a cornerstone on which democratic societies are built, and through them the rule of law is enforced³³.

It is the judiciary which is entrusted with the power to decide whether an individual's right should be sacrificed (and to what extent) to the interest of the community. The measure of the sacrifice, and the conditions under which the judiciary may intervene, obviously depend on the domestic legislation of each case. Yet, some highlights can be found in *Italgomme* that, due to their broad scope, may also be relevant to other jurisdictions.

The first significant element involves the necessity of judicial review during the tax inspection and pertinent activity of the tax office as soon as this enters into a collision course with fundamental rights protected by the convention. The *ex-post* protection is by definition considered insufficient for this purpose³⁴. This aspect has already been pointed out in literature, as it was observed that the nature of the right potentially infringed during inspections is different from the right of the procedure³⁵.

While the focus of taxation is on applying the law fairly and considering the ability to pay—which may, from the state's perspective, limit certain individual rights—other rights

³¹ Bigham, *cit.*, pp. 90 and *sub*.

³² See for instance ECHR case *Bernh Larsen Holding AS and Others v. Norway*, n. 24117/08, 14 March 2013 in particular at § 105.

³³ M. Greggi and I. Buriani, «La CEDU e il principio del giusto procedimento», *cit.*

³⁴ *Italgomme* at § 103 but see also before ECHR case *Société Canal Plus v. France*, n. 29408/08, 21 December 2010, at § 40.

³⁵ M. Greggi and I. Buriani, «La CEDU e il principio del giusto procedimento», *cit.*

come into play during the process, including privacy of communications, family life, professional secrecy, and so on.

In these circumstances, the fiscal nature of the offence, or the fact that such a potential violation of rights occurs during tax inspection, should not be considered.

The second element, substantive in nature, is the requirement for proportionality between the scope of the activity and the request made by the tax authorities.

The need for proportionality is well recognised in international literature³⁶, having been extensively debated within the context of information exchange procedures. In this regard, it is noted that the obligation to share data (from one administration or another) is limited by the scope of fishing expeditions. In the literature³⁷, a fishing expedition refers to a disproportionate and unselective request for information concerning several unidentified taxpayers, lacking a solid justification.

A common understanding exists regarding the need to reject this kind of request on two main grounds: firstly, because they would violate individual rights on proportionality grounds, and secondly, because they would necessitate an excessive and redundant activity by the requested tax administration to meet the requirements of the requesting parties.

Data collection and data management, as a consequence, face limitations in international tax law, since every intrusion into private life is acceptable in a democratic state only if it is necessary to pursue a public interest.

This principle is very well known in the field of criminal law, where the instances of protection are of the highest level. In that domain, access and inspections can actually be carried out via coercive instruments and the use of force, which is usually defined in tax inspection in most states. Moreover, in the field of taxation, every taxpayer has the duty to cooperate with the tax administration³⁸: such a duty does not exist in criminal law, where, although to different extents, the person investigated has the right to self-defence, including the right to remain silent and not to assist the police if they believe that this behaviour best protects their position.

Yet, according to the court, a similarity between the two positions exists: if the taxpayer does not comply with the order to the tax office, his position in the trial would be impaired

³⁶ Jonas Christoffersen, *Fair Balance: A Study of Proportionality, Subsidiarity and Primarity in the European Convention on Human Rights* (Brill, 2009).

³⁷ Liesa Keunen, «Big Data Tax Audits: The Conceptualisation of Fishing Expeditions», *International Review of Law, Computers & Technology* 37, fasc. 2 (2023): 166–97, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13600869.2023.2192568>.

³⁸ *Italgomme* at § 81 “the Court reiterates that tax audits complement the duty of a taxpayer to provide the tax authorities with accurate information to enable them to make a correct tax assessment (...)” See also ECHR case *Rustamkhanli v. Azerbaijan*, n. 24460/16, 4 July 2024 at § 36.

as the documents whose delivery has been omitted (although requested) would not be admissible in court. Moreover, he would be exposed to a more aggressive form of audit and presumptive determination of tax (allegedly) evaded.

In other words, since the consequences of the lack of collaboration are significantly adverse to the taxpayer (while they aren't to the person under investigation), the same metric can be used and criminal and tax procedures can be evaluated on the same ground.

Once this point has been clarified, the Court proceeds with the analysis and evaluates the possible infringement of Article 8 in the circumstances of the case. Consistent with well-established case law, the Court does not evaluate domestic law as it stands, but rather the application of it in the specific case.

In this situation, the combined presence of several factors leads to the conclusion regarding the probable infringement of Article 8.

Firstly, the taxpayer's request for collaboration was extensive and resembled a fishing expedition³⁹. Secondly, the taxpayer was informed that any lack of cooperation or failure to supply documents as requested during this fishing expedition could lead to adverse consequences for their position within the inspection process. Thirdly, such a request for access and document submission was made without any judicial review or oversight by the judiciary. Furthermore, the order to close was not justified, as such a condition is not required under the legislation in this case.

Furthermore, any violation that occurs during the inspection would not find remedies in the judicial phase. At that stage, the tax judiciary's only power is to declare the audit null and void, and nothing more. The judge has no authority to compensate the taxpayer for any possible violation of personal rights suffered, for instance, due to a disproportionate duration of the audit or an intrusive police activity⁴⁰.

Although, in theory, such a possibility is granted to another judge (the civil judge), whose authority is to compensate damages resulting from torts suffered, this has almost never occurred in the judicial history of the state in question⁴¹.

Hence, the violation of Article 8 necessitates the state's intervention to amend the legislation in the case.

³⁹ *Italgomme* at § 84 “In the present case, it is undisputed that the domestic authorities requested a significant amount of information which went beyond the scope of the access in question (...)”.

⁴⁰ *Italgomme* at § 66.

⁴¹ In judgment n. 8587 of 2 May 2016, the Combined Divisions of the Italian Supreme Court ruled that the Civil jurisdiction applies to compensation requests filed by taxpayers who suffered from allegedly disproportionate inspections.

Italy has actually slightly changed the previous legislation in the matter⁴², now imposing a duty on the office to motivate access and streamlining the inspection process. Nothing has been done to broaden the judicial review of the earlier phase of taxpayer control.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS: THE LONG JOURNEY AHEAD FOR EFFECTIVE TAXPAYERS' RIGHTS PROTECTION

When *Italgomme's* decision was delivered, it was celebrated as a revolutionary ruling by the mainstream literature. It was regarded as a groundbreaking measure in terms of taxpayers' rights protection, and domestic authorities hailed it as the start of a new era in the relationship between taxpayers and the tax office.

Although these statements undoubtedly have some ground and reason, they are also heavily influenced by optimism. It is uncommon for a sentence to overhaul decades of extensive legislation and alter *modus operandi*, especially when such a decision could adversely affect the power of the tax authority and, consequently, the effectiveness of anti-evasion efforts.

Italgomme is, in this respect, a good step in the right direction, but the road ahead remains relatively long.

The case was decided under exceptional circumstances, and while it advocates for increased judicial oversight of the tax inspection, it does not impose this. At no point in the judgment do the circumstances of the case violate Article 8 ECHR solely because no judicial authority authorised the tax office to commence investigation; such a statement is not supported by the case itself, though many authors would consider it reasonable and necessary.

The decision was made amid a “perfect storm” affecting taxpayers' rights: an excessive demand, a threat of harsh sanctions, a lack of motivation, and, ultimately, (alleged) aggressive behaviour from the tax office, coupled with the absence of actual remedies *ex post* for those violations.

The combined presence of all these conditions has led the court to decide the *Italgomme* case in this direction and to assess a violation of Article 8 of the European Convention on Human Rights.

⁴² Now Article 12, §1 of the Taxpayers' Bill of Rights in Italy reads as follows (the part not italic has been added with decree 17 June 2025, n. 84 right after *Italgomme*: “All accesses, inspections, and tax audits in premises used for commercial, industrial, agricultural, artistic, or professional activities are carried out based on actual investigative and control needs on-site. In the authorization documents and in the reports drafted pursuant to paragraph 4, the circumstances and conditions that justified the access must be expressly and adequately indicated and motivated. They take place, except in exceptional and urgent cases that are properly documented, during the regular operating hours of the activities and in such a way as to cause the least possible disruption to the conduct of the activities as well as to the taxpayer's commercial or professional relationships.”

A more suitable starting point would have led the Court to argue that, in accordance with the principle, in every state where the rule of law is upheld, judicial control over investigative activities is necessary, and judicial review may be required. We are fully aware that taxation has a particular necessity and that tax *exceptionalism* plays a significant role; nonetheless, a balance should be struck, and minimal protection regarding the methods of inspection should be provided.

Such protection should also be regulated by law as decided by the parliament, not by other public administration bodies, as the Court appears to tolerate in its references to the quality of law at every level of the decision.

No genuine protection of taxpayer rights can exist unless it is granted by the body that represents their will. Such a body should play a role in shaping the law that governs both substantive and procedural tax law, as the distinction between the two is increasingly questionable and ultimately unreasonable nowadays.